
Job Role Stress among Engineering College Teachers of Bareilly District an Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT

This study explores job role stress among engineering college teachers in the Bareilly district, focusing on how stress differs between teachers working in government and private colleges. A sample of 200 teachers was surveyed using Pareek's (1983) Organizational Role Stress Scale. The results show that private college teachers experience higher levels of role-related stress, including more inters role distance, role erosion, self-role distance, and overall stress, compared to government college teachers. The study also found gender differences: female teachers reported higher inter role distance and slightly higher stress in other areas. In addition, younger and less experienced teachers were found to face more stress especially related to balancing roles, feelings of inadequacy, and unclear job expectations than older and more experienced teachers. These findings highlight how factors like the type of institution, age, and teaching experience influence the stress levels of engineering educators. The study suggests that colleges should improve working conditions, offer stress-management programmes, provide opportunities for career growth, and create a positive and supportive work environment to reduce stress and improve

Introduction:-

The modern world, which is said to be a world of achievements, is also a world of stress. One finds stress everywhere, whether it be within the family, business organization any other social or economic activity. Right from the time of birth till the last breath drawn, an individual is invariably exposed to various stressful situations. Thus, it is not surprising that interest in the issue has been rising with the advancement of the present century, which has been called the 'Age of Stress'.

The concept of stress dates back to 1914, the stress were derived from the Latin word "Strangers". Stress was popularly used in the seventeenth century to mean hardship, strain, adversity or affliction. Cofer and Appley (1964) defined stress as state of an organism in which his/her well-being or integrity was perceived to be endangered. Hall and Mansfield (1971) referred to stress as an external force operating on a system, be that system an organization or a person. According to Lazarus and his colleagues (1984) stress is defined by the interaction of an external agent and characteristics of the object. Sen (1981) found that the higher an individual is in the organizational hierarchy, the more sector organizations experience significantly more stress than those of private sector - organization. Beena and Poduval (1991) found that stress experience of the executives increased age. Sex was also found to be a major factor affecting the stress condition."

Lambert and Lambert (1993) revealed significant negative correlation role stress and psychological hardiness and between components of job role stress and components of hardiness. In another study, Grover and Sen (1994) found managers to be experiencing less job study related to bank professionals conducted by Pattanayak and Mishra (1997) revealed that to stress and expressed greater organizational commitment as compared to supervisors. Another adequate time allocation for problem solving, recasting the right kind of people for the jobs and counteract the ill-effects of stress, professional management on the part of the organization, attracting highly qualified personnel with high compensation packages, and an expressive work ethic on the part of the employees might prove useful. Haque and Khan (2001) observed that the relationship between homework stress and burnout was moderated by organizational sources of support predominantly in nurses whereas Shyam et al., (2004) found organizational job role stress to be strongly and positively correlated with emotional exhaustion and depersonalization dimensions of burnout. Further the younger and less experienced health

professionals were found to experience greater organizational job role stress than their older and more experienced counter parts.

Keeping in view the importance of job stress, it was thought worthwhile to look into job stress among Engineering college Teachers. The present study is a humble effort in this direction to compare job stress among private and public sector engineering teachers taking into account the gender difference as well. Further, experience and age, in combination with type of banking, confound in enhancing or decreasing levels of organizational job stress, is explored.

Objectives of the Study:-

1. To compare job role stress and its dimensions among government and private Engineering College.
2. To study gender differences in job stress and its dimensions among private engineering college teachers.
3. To study job role stress and its dimensions among private engineering teachers in relation to age and teaching experience.

Methodology:-

Survey method was used for the conduct of the present study.

Sample of the Study:-

A random sample of 200 private engineering teachers working in private and public private engineering college was drawn.

Research Tool:-

Organizational Role Stress Scale developed by Pareek (1983) was used to assess job role stress among engineering teachers.

Analysis of Data:-

The use of t-test was made to study role stress and its dimensions in engineering college teachers in terms of type of college and-gender. Correlation was used to study the relationship-of job role stress with-age and experience,

Results:-

The results of the study are as under:

(i) Organizational Role Stress among Private Engineering College and Government engineering College teachers

The private and government engineering college teachers were found to differ significantly on inter-role distance ($t = 5.60, p < .01$), role erosion ($t = 3.90, p < .01$), self-role distance ($t = 1.98, p < .05$) dimensions of job role stress and total role stress ($t = 2.09, p < .05$). Further, the private engineering college teachers experienced significantly higher levels of inter-role distance, role erosion, self-role distance and role stress as compared to their counterparts from government schools.

(ii) Gender differences in Organizational Role Stress

The results of the study revealed significant gender differences in inter-role distance dimension of role stress only ($t = 2.53, p < .01$). Further, female engineering college teachers were found to exhibit significantly higher inter-role distance than their male counterparts. Similarly, role stagnation, role erosion, role overload, role inadequacy, personal inadequacy and role stress for female school teachers were also found to be higher than their male counterparts, though not significantly so.

(iii) Organizational job Role Stress in relation to age and teaching experience

The correlational analysis revealed significant, but negative correlation of inter-role distance ($r = -0.48, p < .01$), role-erosion ($r = -0.27, p < .01$), self-role distance ($r = -0.27, p < .01$), personal inadequacy ($r = -0.20, p < .05$) and total organizational role stress ($r = -0.27, p < .01$) with age indicating that younger school teachers experience more role stress, inter-role distance, role erosion, personal inadequacy and self-role distance in comparison to their older counterparts. Similarly inter-role distance ($r = -0.50, p < .01$), role erosion ($r = -0.22, p < .05$), self role distance ($r = -0.27, p < .01$), and total role stress ($r = -0.24, p < .05$), were found to be significantly but negatively correlated with teaching experience. It shows that less experienced / school teachers exhibit more inter-role distance, role erosion, self role distance and organizational role stress as compared to their more experienced counterparts.

Discussion:-

Private engineering college teachers were found to experience significantly higher levels of inter-role distance, role erosion, self-role distance and role stress as compared to their government engineering college counterparts. These findings of the study are in line with the previous researches. Beena & Poduval(1991) and aditya and Sen(1993). Higher dimension-wise as well as overall role stress scores in case of female engineering college teachers can be attributed to the fact that working females try hard to make a balance between their family and work place whereas males are comparatively at an advantage. Younger college teachers were found to experience significantly greater inter-role distance, role erosion, personal inadequacy, self-role distance and role stress in comparison to their older counterparts. The role stress experienced by college teachers who were younger may be due to the greater amount of efforts put in by them. The results conform to the findings of Shyam et.al., (2004) and Choudhary (1990). However, Beena and Poduwal (1991) found stress to increase with age.

Further, less experienced college teachers possess significantly higher inter-role distance, role erosion, Self-role distance and role stress as compared to their more experienced counterparts Judkins (2002) and Shyam et.al., (2004) also found younger and less experienced health professionals to be highly stressed in comparison to their older and more experienced counterparts.

Implications:-

Modern management approaches encourage the development of high morale, team spirit and other positive factors at the workplace to enhance the well-being of staff. the expected outcome is high productivity, loyalty, a team approach to problem solving, etc. So, it is suggested that the work environment of private engineering college teachers should be modified. Vakola & Nikolaou (2005), taking into account the following factors:

- A well designed stress reduction program should be implemented. The strategies should be directed towards improving the conditions of work such as improving career ladders, modifying the use of training and technology, job rotation and enrichment, and increasing skill levels.
- Morale in a work group should be high. High levels of morale can be maintained by ensuring that the efforts of staff members are acknowledged periodically. Staff should be praised for good work.

- Workload levels can be one of the most contentious issues in the relationship between manager and staff member. Conflict between staff can reduce overall productivity.

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